

THE ADVANTAGES OF USING THE ONLINE RESOURCES IN TEACHING ENGLISH.

Baykhanova Nilufar Alisherovna

Tashkent State Agrarian University, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

kadirovanilufar77@gmail.com

Annotation

This article acknowledges the advantages of using the online resources in teaching English in higher education institutions and extensively researches and experiences on this topic.

Key words: online resources, education, language learning, methods, environment.

Introduction

Language teachers have increasingly harnessed its power for language pedagogy. This study aimed to investigate the use of online resources and applications by language teachers and the purposes for which they use them for language teaching.

Online resources can improve the quality of education in many ways. Teachers use online materials to prepare lessons, and students to extend their range of learning. While access to current English books or newspapers may not be easy, you can always use the internet to find content on almost any topic. You can practice your English language learning by reading books or newspaper articles, listening to the radio or podcasts and by watching streaming videos or films on TV. The Internet is also preserving certain regional dialects, such as Southern English, that previously would have faded. The Internet has spawned a language revolution, the likes of which have never been seen before. We can instantly share photos, post news stories, and just chat with friends, family, and colleagues from anywhere in the world with an internet connection. Blogs that deal with the English language, websites that host grammar handbooks and dictionaries are all great resources for improving your English. Teachers can also make use of the internet by providing the students with extra study materials and resources such as interactive lessons, educational quiz as

well as tutorials. Teachers can record their lectures and provide them to the students for revisions which are better than reading from notes. Moreover, Internet is the most useful technology of modern times which helps us not only in our daily lives but also in professional lives. It is no doubt that in this modern era everyone prefers Google for their queries, problems or doubts. Popular search engines like Google, Yahoo, etc. are the topmost choice of people as they offer an easy and instant reach to the vast amount of information in just a few seconds. Of course, we search from internet resources, for instance handouts, texts, books, which is so easy for us. Sometime we have not enough time to create our own handouts. At that internet resources help us. There are many resources on the Internet for language learning. These resources can be easily given to learners by selecting them according to their levels. We can always look for the resources we need from various internet sites. There will be some difficulties right but these are temporary. The biggest advantages of using the internet to support your language learning is how much it can help you to understand the culture of another country.

As well, a variety of online educational methods are being developed, and potential students should consider some of the identifiable factors common to all types of enrolled courses and programs. For example, they can learn from home or at work using computers. Over time, several companies have come on the market to provide costly educational apps for all levels of students and promote their best technologies and methods for delivering online learning content. The benefits of online learning and teaching have gained mass acceptance over time. And, with the situation created by the COVID-19 pandemic, global educators, educational institutions, and students seem to be more enthusiastic about online learning due to the pandemic and lockdown madness, and the need for online learning has increased. Online learning methods can be an effective alternative educational medium for mature and self-disciplined students, but they may not be suitable for learning environments that depend on learners. Students must be organized, self-motivated, and have a high level of time management to maintain the course while participating in an online program. Asynchronous online education gives students control over their learning experience, gives non-traditional students flexibility in the curriculum, and puts greater

responsibility on students. Many students aren't comfortable asking questions in class for fear of feeling stupid. Most of us, instructors included, put off the things we need to do until the very last moment. When it comes to education, the last moment is the worst possible moment to learn. Sometimes that lesson is learned the hard way in the form of poor performance on an exam or assignment. But ultimately, you succeed because you realize the importance of doing things on time or even ahead of time. That self-realization propels your success in an online course. The online student takes responsibility for their course of studies and matures into an individual for whom learning and accomplishment are highly valued. In short, your success depends on you. Online teaching require more time than on campus classes. If you are sitting in a classroom, it's likely that you'll miss a good percentage of what the instructor says, no matter how focused you are. It's human nature to zone out for brief periods of time. Many students claim that there are more disadvantages to online learning. Parents of students who have switched to distance learning and students of online courses have found that it is difficult to learn alone. If an online program is to be successful, its students must be able to access an online learning environment. If participants have a time limit on the internet access they can afford for classes, participation in the program is not fair for all students. Distance learning limits students to classes based on learning materials. As students learn online, their education is more important than ever in the modern world. Instead of the traditional role of teachers leading the class, the learning experience tends to focus more on students, and as a result, students are more active and accountable for learning. Online education is a complex solution that allows students to learn from home and acquire qualified knowledge and practical skills.

Besides, advantage of the Internet is the ability to access all types of information from library resources all over the world, including magazines, books, newspapers and journal publications, instantaneously. This information increases the learning potential by providing students with the latest information. They use the internet so much around the world that it seems hard to imagine a world without the internet right now. The Internet can motivate the students, make teaching more fun, and allows variation in teaching. Four

major drawbacks of the use of the Internet were reported by the teachers, students' cheating, unreliable information, technical problems, and students' extracurricular activities during lessons. Teachers also have a lot more resources at their fingertips, which can greatly improve their lesson planning process. The Internet has a universal appeal for most people. We in the Uzbekistan have become dependent on it for our daily routines. We shop, send mail, read the news, look up movie reviews, etc., using the Internet. We depend on this service, because we have told ourselves that "It" has made our lives easier. We use of similar technologies within the classroom, because we are convinced that the use of computers and having access to the Internet is the best way to educate our children so they can have an equal chance to reach their potential and accomplish their goals. It is true that the Internet is a great source of information. Its value as a resource is immeasurable.

In the realm of education, I think that the Internet can be a great resource of information. Research can be easily planned and implemented for the benefit of both students and educators. Unfortunately, this brings us back to the issue of limited access. Some students are more readily exposed and connected to this source than others. It would be unfair for educators to expect all students to access Internet sources for their education, unless this is implemented as part of the curriculum. The Internet is a great research tool. I think that all students at the university level should be proficient at using it. I also know that these skills are better learned when taught from a young age; therefore, the sooner we teach students to use the internet the faster the students will pick it up and be able to learn to reap its benefits.

References:

1. <https://www.cambridgeenglish.org/teaching-english/resources-for-teachers/general-english-resources/>
2. <https://www.i-to-i.com/tefl-blog/tefl-classroom-and-expert-advice/8-best-resources-teaching-english-online/>

3. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/374320653> EXPLORING THE USE OF ONLINE RESOURCES FOR ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING STUDENTS' PERSPECTIVES

4. <https://ciencialatina.org/index.php/cienciala/article/view/8176/12344>

